

LIFETIME STATISTICS FOR SINGLE KEVLAR® 49 FILAMENTS IN CREEP-RUPTURE AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

Kevlar® 49 fibrous composites are routinely fabricated to have strengths above 1.5 GPa (200 ksi), but in many applications (cables, pressure vessels, flywheels) one would like to reliably sustain such stresses for long times. The present paper reports results from an experimental study of the lifetime of single Kevlar® 49 filaments under constant stress at 80° C and 130° C. The work is a continuation of that reported on earlier at 21° C with the goal being to fully characterize the statistical strength and lifetime of the individual filaments in order to separate fiber effects from fiber/matrix interactions in the creep-rupture of larger composite structures. The lifetime data were well modeled by a Weibull distribution with shape parameter values ranging from about 0.2 at 21° C to about 0.9 at 130° C. The sensitivity of lifetime to load level and temperature was well modeled by an exponential molecular breakdown model of the Eyring-Zhurkov type. An activation energy of 80 kcal/mole, was obtained suggesting scission of the C-N bond as the dominant mechanism in long term failure.

INTRODUCTION

One of the major concerns in many applications for composite materials is the service lifetime under sustained loads that are significant fractions of the short term tensile strength of the material. Experiments carried out on Kevlar® 49/epoxy strands and pressure vessels, such as those at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory reported by Phoenix and Wu [1] and Gerstle and Kunz [2], have been both costly and inconclusive, partly as a result of unanticipated problems with UV light degradation and earthquakes. Phoenix and Wu [1],

interpreting these data, have shown that both strand strength and lifetime behave in ways not predicted using a simple 'rule of mixtures'. Gerstle and Kunz [2] noted that a significant amount of the variability in the lifetime of pressure vessels could be attributed to variation in properties among the spools of yarn used to wind the pressure vessels. It is clear from results that both spool-to-spool variability and the matrix play important roles, but these cannot be determined precisely without first having data on individual Kevlar® 49 filaments.

Motivated by these findings, Wagner, Phoenix and Schwartz [3] studied the statistical variability in the strength and diameter of single Kevlar® 49 filaments at ambient conditions (21° C and 65% r.h.). The filaments were sampled from two spools from a common production lot (no.74048), labelled A and B. Spool A was found to have typical variability (10% cv) in linear density (mass/unit length), and Spool B had unusually high variability (25% cv), where cv is coefficient of variation (standard deviation/mean). They found virtually identical variability in the failure stress (12% cv) of filaments drawn from each of the two spools. Studying the lifetime in creep-rupture of these filaments, also at ambient conditions, Wagner, Schwartz and Phoenix [4] found that the median lifetime of filaments drawn from spool B was an order of magnitude larger than that of the filaments drawn from spool A, when subjected to identical stress levels. However when the stresses were normalized by the failure stress of that particular spool, the difference in lifetimes between the two spools disappeared. The lifetime data at each stress level generally fit a two-parameter Weibull distribution with shape parameter values near 0.2. These data are recounted in later discussion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology and equipment for the present study were similar to that described in [4], and the same two spools A and B were used as a source of the filaments. Short-term (static) strength results were conducted at a strain rate of 0.1/min using an Instron Model TM tension test machine fitted with an environmental chamber to control temperature. Several commercial adhesives were screened for use in tabbing the specimens at elevated temperatures. We selected a high temperature resistant epoxy, Omegabond 101, as the clamping medium for the standard paper tabs. The sample size at each temperature was typically 50 filaments. Important to our procedure was the measurement of the cross-sectional area of each filament using a specially built vibroscope. The data were successfully fitted to a two-parameter Weibull distribution,

$$F(x) = 1 - \exp[-(x/a)^b], \quad x \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

where a and b are the Weibull scale and shape parameters, respectively.

Lifetime data at 80° C and 130° C were of interest to supplement the previous data at 21° C. For this purpose our creep-rupture rack with 48 stations was inserted into a large, forced-air oven. Special precautions were taken to suppress vibration and to shield specimens

from air currents. Modifications in the timing and loading systems were made to improve the resolution at short times over that obtained earlier [4]. The stress levels were chosen as suitable fractions (between 0.55 and 0.925) of the Weibull scale parameter for short term strength for that temperature. Again for these tests, the cross-sectional area of each filament was measured such that individually tailored weights could be made to apply the desired stress. The number of filaments for each test level was typically 48. Important aspects to the data were the number of failures on loading, the number still surviving at the censor time (Type I) which was typically 168 hours. The lifetime data were fitted at each stress level to a two-parameter Weibull distribution using the method of maximum likelihood for censored data. In this case the Weibull scale and shape parameters were denoted as r and s respectively.

RESULTS

With respect to short-term strength, Table 1 presents the respective Weibull shape and scale parameters for the tension tests at various temperatures. Note the reduction in the scale parameter values for strength with increasing temperature, whereas the shape parameter values remain remarkably constant.

TABLE 1

Maximum likelihood estimates of the Weibull scale (\hat{a}) and shape (\hat{b}) parameters for filament strength at various temperatures

Spool	Temperature [°C]	\hat{b}	\hat{a} [MPa]
A	21	10.2	3538
	80	10.1	3304
	130	10.5	3019
	180	10.7	2879
B	21	10.4	3594
	80	10.2	3385
	130	10.1	3041
	180	10.2	2751

With respect to the lifetime data, Figure 1 shows a typical plot of the data on Weibull coordinates. Tables 2 and 3 give the resulting lifetime Weibull parameter estimates.

Figure 1. Weibull probability plots for filament lifetime data.
 (Spools A and B at 130°C and 55 % stress ratio.)

TABLE 2

Maximum likelihood estimates of the Weibull scale (\hat{r}) and shape (\hat{s}) parameters
for filament lifetime at 80° C

Stress Ratio [%]	Spool A			Spool B		
	\hat{r} [h]	\hat{s}	Median [h]	\hat{r} [h]	\hat{s}	Median [h]
92.5	-	-	-	0.032	0.39	0.012
90	0.317	0.38	0.043	0.058	0.37	0.050
85	0.594	0.29	0.167	0.129	0.41	0.053
80	2.09	0.29	0.591	0.804	0.39	0.311
70	196.	0.38	75.3	64.5	0.29	18.2
65	1077.	0.30	314.	374.	0.29	105.

TABLE 3

Maximum likelihood estimates of the Weibull scale (\hat{r}) and shape (\hat{s}) parameters
for filament lifetime at 130° C

Stress Ratio [%]	Spool A			Spool B		
	\hat{r} [h]	\hat{s}	Median [h]	\hat{r} [h]	\hat{s}	Median [h]
92.5	0.026	0.35	0.009	-	-	-
90	0.046	0.38	0.017	0.025	0.49	0.012
85	0.200	0.41	0.081	0.112	0.46	0.051
80	0.420	0.47	0.193	0.240	0.46	0.109
75	1.19	0.48	0.878	0.501	0.47	0.299
70	5.73	0.50	2.74	2.34	0.51	1.15
60	33.4	0.78	20.9	16.5	0.67	9.56
55	93.2	0.99	64.4	78.3	1.03	54.9

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The data were interpreted using both a power law format (linear behavior on log load versus log time coordinates) and an exponential breakdown law format (linear behavior on load versus log time coordinates). The latter format is based on the activation energy ideas of Eyring [5] and Zhurkov [6]. See Wagner, Schwartz and Phoenix [4] for a complete discussion of the power law format. First it was found that the behavior at short times was very different from that at long times in that, in both formats, the relationship of lifetime to stress level changed drastically; this suggested perhaps different molecular mechanisms of failure. Also the relationship of short term strength to long term life differed slightly for the two spools as did the effect of temperature on both of these. (We note that spool B had a very broad filament diameter distribution relative to that of spool A suggesting perhaps differences in processing history.) Figure 2 shows a plot of the Weibull scale parameter values for lifetime in the power law format. The power law exponent ρ is the inverse of the (negative) slope on this scaling. (To enhance the display of the data all on one graph, we rescaled slightly the absolute stress levels for spool A relative to those of spool B. The adjustments for spool A were a 7.5% increase at 21 ° C and decreases of 3% and 4% at 80 ° C and 130 ° C respectively.) Also the times associated with the short term strength results are effective times calculated as in [4].

Figure 3 shows a plot of the Weibull scale parameters for lifetime at each temperature on load versus log time coordinates; the previously described effects can be seen. For longer times we considered a Zhurkov-Eyring law for the scale parameter, r , in the form

$$r = \tau_0 \exp\{(U_0 - \gamma L)/(\tilde{k} \tilde{T})\} \quad (2)$$

where U_0 is the so-called activation energy of the molecular failure event, γ is the activation volume, \tilde{k} is Boltzmann's constant, \tilde{T} is the absolute temperature, and τ_0 is a period of bond vibration. For the lines shown on Figure 3 the corresponding parameter values are (in familiar units)

$$U_0 \cong 80 \text{ kcal/mole,}$$

$$\gamma \cong 0.166 \text{ (nm)}^3,$$

and

$$\tau_0 \cong 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ seconds .}$$

The above activation energy value is consistent with that generally quoted for the scission of the C-N bond in Kevlar 49 fibers. Also the activation volume value seems realistic (though its magnitude seems to reflect some stress concentration effects). The dotted lines, shown at short times, are estimates of the behavior based on tension tests at various strain rates.

Figure 2. Adjusted absolute stress level versus Weibull scale parameter for lifetime at three temperatures on log-log coordinates.

Figure 3. Adjusted absolute stress level versus Weibull scale parameter for lifetime at three temperatures on semi-log coordinates.

It is clear that the power-law version of the model with the molecular interpretation as described in Phoenix [7] and Phoenix and Kuo [8] and used in Wagner, Schwartz and Phoenix [4] is not particularly successful for this data. A major difficulty may be the wide stress range involved which overextends the power law, molecular modeling especially at lower stress levels. On the other hand, the exponential breakdown law format seems to be successful at lower stress levels and longer times, but not at the highest stress levels where additional molecular failure phenomena seem to be involved. It is also important to note that the value of the time constant τ_0 is ten orders of magnitude larger than the 10^{-12} seconds usually taken as the bond vibration frequency. We are presently using the modeling approach of Phoenix [7] and Phoenix and Kuo [8] under the exponential breakdown format to explain this phenomenon, and preliminary results are encouraging. These results will be reported on elsewhere.

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